

Supplementary Material

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar ATGGAGTCAGTGGATCCTCTAGTGGCCGGAAAGGTGATCG
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 ATGGAGTCAGTGGATCCTCTAGTGGCCGGAAAGGTGATCG

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar GAGATGTTGTTCGACATGTTT TTCCGGCAGTTGAGTTTAC
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 GAGATGTTGTTCGACATGTTG TTCCGGCAGTTGAGTTTAC

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar TGTCGAATATGCTTCCAAACAAATAACGAATAATGGAGTT
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 TGTCGAATATGCTTCCAAACAAATAACGAATAATGGAGTT

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar GAAATTAACCGGCTGCAGCTGCACAAAAGCCAAGAGTTC
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 GAAATTAACCGGCTGCAGCTGCACAAAAGCCAAGAGTTC

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar ATATAAAGGGTTCTCCTGATTCTAATAATCTTTACACCCCT
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 ATATAAAGGGTTCTCCTGATTCTAATAATCTTTACACCCCT

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar TGTAAATGGCTGATCCAGATGCTCCTAGTCCCCTCAACCA
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 TGTAAATGGCTGATCCAGATGCTCCTAGTCCCCTCAACCA

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar ACTTTTAGAGAATGGCTCCATTGGATTGTCACGGATATTC
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 ACTTTTAGAGAATGGCTCCATTGGATTGTCACGGATATTC

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar CAGAGGGAGCCGATGCCTCTCGAGGTAGGGAGGTGATTGA
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 CAGAGGGAGCCGATGCCTCTCGAGGTAGGGAGGTGATTGA

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar ATATATGGGACCTCAGCCACCAGCAGGGATACATCGATAC
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 ATATATGGGACCTCAGCCACCAGCAGGGATACATCGATAC

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar GTGTTTCGCGCTGTTTAGGCAGAGAGAGGCAGAGCAAGTAC
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 GTGTTTCGCGCTGTTTAGGCAGAGAGAGGCAGAGCAAGTAC

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar CCCATAAACCAACCAGGGCGTTCCAATTTAAGACTCG
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 CCCATAAACCAACCAGGGCGTTCCAATTTAAGACTCG

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar TCAGTTTGCAAGTGACAATGGACTTGGTCTTCCTGTGGCT
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 TCAGTTTGCAAGTGACAATGGACTTGGTCTTCCTGTGGCT

SmMFT-2_Ramnagar GCTCTTTATTTTATTTTACACAAGGAACGTTAG
SmMFT-2_Smer_r2.5.1 GCTCTTTATTTTATTTTACACAAGGAACGTTAG

Figure S1. Comparison of *MFT-2* gene mined from *Sme_r2.5.1* and the corresponding transcript of *S. melongena* (Ramnagar Giant). Black background denotes bases with similarities whereas white background denotes variation.

Figure S2. The coding sequence (CDS) of SmFT-5 as predicted using Fgenesh gene prediction tool. The CDS encodes regions which include Transcription Start Site (TSS) and poly-A tail. CDSf indicates the first CDS (which starts with a start codon), CDSi indicates internal exon, CDSo indicates outer exon, and CDSl indicates the last coding sequence (which ends with a stop codon).

Table S1. Sequences of primers used in the first round of PCR

Primer Identity	Sequence (direction 5' to 3')
CEN1_FOR	/5AmMC6/gcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcacCTC CTC CTT TGC AAC ATT ATC A
CEN2_FOR	/5AmMC6/gcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcacGGT CCC ATA TTT TTT ATG CCT TC
CEN4_FOR	/5AmMC6/gcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcacCCT TTA ATC TTG AAG CCT GAA CA
TFL1_FOR	/5AmMC6/gcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcacGTA TTT TGC ACT TCT CTT CTC AC
MFT1_FOR	/5AmMC6/gcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcacCGT AAG TGA CCA AAA TCC TTG TAA
MFT2_FOR	/5AmMC6/gcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcacCAG CCA CGT CAG CAT TAA CAT GA
CEN1_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagGTA CAA AGT CGT TGT ACT AGC A
CEN2_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagATG GAT CAA TCA AAC GCT ACT AAG
CEN3_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagGGA CCA AAA TAT TGA CGA CAA AG
CEN4_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagCTA CAT GAT GCA TGA ACA TGA CA
TFL1_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagGAA GAG AGT AAA CAA CAC TAA CC
MFT1_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagGTG CCA AAA CAG AAA ACA CAC AA
MFT2_REV	/5AmMC6/ tggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtagACG AGT CGT GAC ATG AAA CAG TA

Table S2. Sequences of primers used in the second round of PCR

Primer Identity	Sequence (direction 5' to 3')
bc_1002_For	/5phos/ACACACAGACTGTGAGGgcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcac
bc_1005_For	/5phos/CACTCGACTCTCGCGTgcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcac
bc_1006_For	/5phos/CATATATATCAGCTGTgcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcac
bc_1007_For	/5phos/TCTGTATCTCTATGTGgcagtcgaacatgtagctgactcaggtcac
bc_1010_Rev	/5phos/CTCTGAGATAGCGCGTtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag
bc_1011_Rev	/5phos/ATAGATATACGTATAGtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag
bc_1012_Rev	/5phos/ACACGCGATCTAGTGTtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag
bc_1013_Rev	/5phos/CTCGCGTATGCGAGAGtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag
bc_1014_Rev	/5phos/ACGCGCGGTAGTGAGtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag
bc_1015_Rev	/5phos/ACACACGTGTCATGCGtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag
bc_1016_Rev	/5phos/ATACTATCTCTCTATGtggatcacttgtgcaagcatcacatcgtag

Table S3. Primer combinations used in the second round of PCR based on cultivars

Cultivar	Plant Sample	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer
Surya	Sample1	bc_1006_For	bc_1010_Rev
	Sample2	bc_1006_For	bc_1011_Rev
	Sample3	bc_1006_For	bc_1012_Rev
EP-47 Annamalai	Sample1	bc_1005_For	bc_1012_Rev
	Sample2	bc_1005_For	bc_1013_Rev
	Sample3	bc_1005_For	bc_1014_Rev
Pant Samrat	Sample1	bc_1007_For	bc_1014_Rev
	Sample2	bc_1007_For	bc_1015_Rev
	Sample3	bc_1007_For	bc_1016_Rev
Arka Nidhi	Sample1	bc_1002_For	bc_1013_Rev
	Sample2	bc_1002_For	bc_1014_Rev
	Sample3	bc_1002_For	bc_1015_Rev

Table S4. Distribution of unmutated *SmMFT-2* alleles in the mutant populations of cultivars, Surya, EP-47 Annamalai, Pant Samrat and Arka Nidhi.

VI047336			
Sample	Subread Coverage	Amplicon Coverage	Allele
An_1-9	476	184	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_3-8	473	173	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_2-1	475	404	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_6-1	463	222	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_N3	306	81	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_1-7	462	160	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_6-8	199	27	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An_N4-4	473	124	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
An5-11	479	102	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
VI045550			
Sa_9-1	127	64	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Heterozygous			
Sa_9-1	205	85	<i>SmMFT-2-allele2</i>
Sa_B6-1	294	88	<i>SmMFT2-allele1</i>
Heterozygous			
Sa_B6-1	191	60	<i>SmMFT-2-allele2</i>
Sa_3-1	455	282	<i>MFT1-allele1</i>
Sa_4-2	134	34	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Heterozygous			
Sa_4-2	345	65	<i>SmMFT-2-allele2</i>
Sa_B7-2	145	59	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Heterozygous			
Sa_B7-2	339	122	<i>SmMFT-2-allele2</i>
Sa_B3-1	480	112	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Sa_B1-2	470	183	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Sa_7-2	468	105	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
VI045276			
Ry_19-2	471	182	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_18-6	479	184	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_31-3	161	77	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_9-3	485	160	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_36-5	485	162	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_29-3	479	142	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_26-4	474	170	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_9-1	101	66	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_5-1	483	238	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_33-7	481	177	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_31-6	470	312	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_33-5	260	110	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>

Ry_2-1	470	176	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ry_16-4	428	129	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>

VI045274

Ni_6-2	476	164	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ni_6-1	461	180	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ni_5-6	43	9	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
Ni_5-1	234	16	<i>SmMFT-2-allele1</i>
